

Justification of a digitized algorithmic model in the LabVIEW environment for computer research of procedures for monitoring radial runout of gear-wheels in mechanical products

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Abstract. Purpose of the article: In modern conditions, it is necessary to move from traditional algorithmic schemes for studying complex technical systems to digitalized algorithmic models for training qualified specialists in applied mechanics. Therefore, the creation and justification of such a model for determining the manufacturer's risks during final verification of products is the purpose of this work. Methodology: Simulation and statistical modeling of control procedures in the NI LabVIEW 7.1 environment, which provides an appropriate level of computer research automation. Results: The algorithmic model allows predicting the range of values of consumer and producer risks depending on the accuracy of the technological system and the limiting error of the checking system. The application of the Weibull distribution for modeling the stochastic process of formation of radial runout of evolvement gear-wheel surfaces is justified. The values of the Weibull distribution parameters are determined for modeling a stochastic technological system for processing different levels of accuracy: low, normal, high. Academic novelty: graphs reflecting the dependence of the selected reliability index on the limit of tolerated error of the checking system for certain initial data and limitations in the modeling of work processes. Practical implementation: Creating a digital algorithmic model in the LabVIEW environment is equivalent to purchasing a virtual instrument. Positive testing of the described development was carried out during training sessions with master's and postgraduate students studying applied mechanics.

Keywords: Modeling, Monte Carlo method, LabVIEW, manufacturer's risks, limiting error, computer experiments, virtual instrument

1 Introduction

Decisions for choosing options for the components of a technological processing system must be made starting from the first stage of creating innovative technology. The